

Spectrophotometric Determination of Iodochloro- hydroxyquinoline in Multicomponent Pharmaceutical Formulations especially in Presence of Diiodohydroxyquinoline

G. PODDER*

School of Tropical Medicine, Department of Chemistry, Calcutta-700 073

and

T. K. DAS, A. K. SEN and S. K. MOITRA

Central Public Health and Drugs Laboratory, Calcutta-700 015

Manuscript received 23 March 1988, revised 4 July 1988, accepted 20 September 1988

A spectrophotometric method for the estimation of iodochlorohydroxyquinoline based on the quantitative uv absorption maximum at 267 nm of its solution in 3N HCl is described.

IDOCHLOROXYQUINOLINE (ICHQ) is used for the treatment of intestinal amoebiasis and also being used tropically for a wide range of dermatoses¹. The drug ICHQ in tablet dosage form is assayed gravimetrically by the formation of chelate complex with copper acetate². However, the recent official method³ for the estimation of ICHQ as the basic drug employs infrared spectrophotometry, which has been extended for ICHQ cream and ointment³. ICHQ has also been estimated by gas chromatography⁴ and by diverse spectrophotometry method⁵. A careful reappraisal of the methods show that these are either time consuming and laborious or suffer from the disadvantages that the methods can not be used for the determination of the drug ICHQ in presence of diiodohydroxyquinoline (DIHQ).

In this paper we report a simple and elegant spectrophotometric method for determination of the drug ICHQ in multicomponent pharmaceutical formulations based on the quantitative absorption maximum of the drug in 3N HCl at 267 nm. The drug in 3N HCl medium adheres to Beer's law. The absorbance of the reagent at λ_{max} is negligible. Moreover it is also free from variation of position of λ_{max} and absorbance of the drug in 3N HCl medium with respect to reagent concentration. The 3N HCl solution of the drug is stable for 48 h at ambient temperature. The method can be successfully applied for determination of the drug ICHQ present in combination with other drugs especially diiodohydroxyquinoline for which combination no satisfactory method is available.

Experimental

A Shimadzu UV-160 double beam spectrophotometer with 1-cm silica cells were employed for

recording the spectra. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and water used was glass-distilled.

Procedure: Standard ICHQ solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) in 3N HCl was prepared. Different amount of aliquots (0.1-4 ml) of the solution was drawn and sufficient 3N HCl was added to make up a final volume of 100 ml. The absorbance was measured within 48 h at 267 nm against the reagent blank.

Application to various pharmaceutical preparations:

Tablets: (Simple and multicomponent tablets and multicomponent tablets in presence of diiodohydroxyquinoline)

The powdered sample (equivalent to 100 mg of ICHQ) was shaken with 3N HCl (50 ml) for 5 min and diluted to 100 ml with the same reagent and filtered (Whatman No. 1). The first 10 ml of filtrate was discarded and remaining portion was collected. Then 1 ml of the solution was made up to 100 ml with 3N HCl and the absorbance measured within 48 h at 267 nm against the reagent blank and ICHQ content determined.

Ointments and creams: The sample (equivalent to 100 mg of ICHQ) was extracted with 3N HCl (3 × 30 ml) filtered (Whatman No. 1) and volume of the filtrate was made up to 100 ml with 3N HCl. Then 1 ml of the solution was made up to 100 ml with 3N HCl and the ICHQ content determined as above.

Results and Discussion

The drug ICHQ is soluble in 3N HCl and exhibits λ_{max} at 267 nm at ambient temperature. The drug was also taken in a set of HCl concentrations ranging from 0.01 to 6N but quantitative absorbance

maximum was not obtained below 3N HCl. With higher concentrations of HCl the stability fell remarkably. ICHQ does not exhibit any quantitative absorption maximum in alkali and in solvents like ether, chloroform and methanol. Hence 3N HCl was selected as the medium. Diiodohydroxyquinoline (DIHQ) has been found to be almost insoluble in 3N HCl at ambient temperature, hence it does not interfere. DIHQ and ICHQ due to their structural similarity interfere each other in the spectrophotometry assays reported earlier.

Effect of time and temperature : ICHQ is stable in 3N HCl medium for 48 h, thereafter the absorbance falls gradually. The stability of ICHQ in 3N HCl medium was investigated at the temperature range 0–100°. The absorbance values were not affected by temperature in the range 0–60° but fell gradually above this temperature.

Calibration and sensitivity : The calibration plots of ICHQ (concentrations against absorbance) is linear and passes through the origin. Beer's law is obeyed over the range 1–25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for the drug. The molar absorptivity was found to be $2.8 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity⁶ 0.011 ppm.

The results under the above optimum conditions indicate high accuracy and precision of the method. The method was successfully applied to various pharmaceutical formulations, and was compared with compendial methods⁶. The results were found to be highly satisfactory.

Interference : Free iodine, chlorine and iodide and chloride do not interfere.

ICHQ was incorporated with other, drug e.g. diiodohydroxyquinoline, metronidazole, phthalylsulphathiazole, streptomycin sulphate, sulphadimidine, sulphaguanidine, diastase, dried yeast, hydrocortisone, balladonna dry extract, pectin, kaolin, chloroquine phosphate, berberine hydrochloride, backed bael, and papain or diluents and additives such as calcium lactate, lactic acid, zinc stearate, lactose, magnesium trisilicate, dimethyl polysiloxane, magnesium stearate, starch, carboxy methyl cellulose, tartrazine, amaranth and other colouring agents. These substances did not interfere in the analysis of ICHQ by the present method.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. N. N. Chakraborty, Director, Central Public Health and Drugs Laboratory for facilities.

References

1. "Remington's Pharmaceutical Sciences 1985", 17th. ed., Mack Publishing Company, Easton, 18042, p. 1227.
2. "Indian Pharmacopoeia 1985", Controller of Publications, Delhi, 1985, pp. 440-442.
3. "United States Pharmacopoeia 1980", 20th. Rev., U. S. Pharmacopoeial Convention, Rockville, pp. 155, 156.
4. "British Pharmacopoeia 1980", H. M. S. O., London, 1980, p. 115.
5. S. A. ISMAIEL and D. A. YASSA, *Pharmazie*, 1973, 28, 611; R. T. SAVE and A. B. AMBARDEKAR, *Indian Drugs*, 1981, 18, 290; D. M. SHINGBAI and G. B. NATEKAR, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1980, 42, 181; Ref. 4, pp. 546, 547, 699; S. G. KUNDAJI and R. G. TAMHANE, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1978, 35, 90.
6. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 644.